

INTERNET AS A RESOURCE FOR LANGUAGE LEARNING AND TEACHING

Makhmatkulova Yayra

UzSWLU Oriental Philology faculty

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Nowadays as we are dwelling in a world which is called ‘The period of technologies’ it is almost impossible to imagine any field of the study without developments and improvements of the Internet. The system of modern teaching and learning through the Internet is playing a significant role in modern language learning and teaching. In order to meet the opportunities of fast evolving globe and demanding high-tech-environment of the immediate future, it is extremely important to equip students with relevant abilities and aptitudes, especially in online learning and communication skills, and help them to shape correct technology attitude and belief. Several research results show that the usage of the Internet on learning and teaching the language has its own both drawbacks and pros. The main findings display that almost all of the learners and teachers agree with the use of Internet-assisted language instruction and consider technology to be an important approach in their future teaching careers. Nonetheless, about one fourth of teachers in this study still do not have enough certainty and were unsure whether they owe the skills and understandings of techniques to use Internet appropriately in their future lessons.

Beyond the shadow of a doubt, the introduction of the Internet to teaching and learning process is still considered to be a new approach compared with traditional instructions. In the last centuries the role of the internet in pedagogy has already become very essential as educators recognize its comforts to create both independent and collaborative learning environments in which students can acquire and practice their target language (Butler-Pascoe, 1997). In fact, with the rapid development of computer and the Internet, how to integrate technology into curriculum and learning activities become a popular teaching and learning approach in the classrooms. Gitsaki and Taylor (2001) further stated that the advantages of the Internet learning can let students practice English and computer skills at the same time, expose them to rich input of English used in real life situation, enhances students autonomy by allowing students to direct their learning to areas that they are interested in, assist student to communicate with native speakers at any time, and stimulate their learning motivation through various online activities. In highly developed teaching and learning era, complicated research from learners’ perceptions to look over their perceptions toward learning the language with the Internet advancements will be important and useful data for educators to estimate the effectiveness of the Internet language learning and makes the progress of online pedagogy in the foreseeable future.

The importance and benefits of using Internet in inside and outside classroom education will be highly effective. As a learner, one can get the basic knowledge during outside process, as we may have much more time than the inside process. One can just independently learn the language with the help of the Internet. That is the reason why it is better to train as an autonomous learner on the Internet. Several researchers emphasize the benefits of using the Internet while learning the language on the Internet. Here are some points about these benefits:

• *According to the research results and ideas of Meena Singhal (1997), pros of the Internet for the language student are highlighted: ‘The World Wide Web is ... a virtual library at one’s*

fingertips; it is a readilyavailable world of information for the language learner' (Singhal 1997:4). She especially emphasizes the benefits of emailing, which is profitable to use with timid students who can thuscommunicate without having to speak up in lessons being afraid of making up mistakes in front of other learners. Additionally, via email, language learners cancommunicate with native speakers, rendering the communication an authentic context.

• According to Kilimci it is well known that *The World Wide Webprovides teachers and students with a chance of downloadingand listening to any kind of radio programs, television programs,the news etc., thus to listen to native speakers online. Furthermore, the Internet gives a great possibility of getting accessto libraries and a great deal of reading handouts and also the opportunity to familiarize themselves with many different cultures and peoples of the language they are learning(109, 112).*

As it has been analyzed, there is compelling evidence for the effectiveness of the Internet in developing language acquisition. The internet is not only a resource for developing reading and listening but also a perfect tool to develop writing and speaking. Because Internet has the potential of to make teaching language more fun and interesting by getting the best materials for learners, and thus to increase students' motivation to learn easily. Both the teachers and learners are equipped with limitless technical resources such as Internet also can bring perfect achievements in learning and teaching process. There is no doubt that the generations of future internet learners are excellent candidates for assuming productive and proactive roles in shaping their own language learning experiences and thereby shaping second language acquisition.

References:

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